

MINIMUM WEIGHT COMPOSITE TRUSS CORE SANDWICH PANELS SUBJECTED TO COMBINED
UNIAXIAL COMPRESSION AND IN-PLANE SHEAR LOADS

Jack R. Vinson
Department of Mechanical Engineering
University of Delaware
Newark, DE 19716
USA

ABSTRACT

The use of sandwich construction composed of composite materials offers significant weight advantages over other structural architectures and materials for many load applications. Still, it is important to develop means to attain minimum weight composite sandwich panels to take full advantage of their potential. This includes a rationale for selecting the best materials among numerous alternatives, and the best stacking sequences for these competing material systems.

Among various sandwich panel core alternatives, truss core looks very competitive with honeycomb core, web core and solid core under simultaneous loadings where uniaxial loads are fairly significant. In the present study involving the truss core sandwich subjected to combined uniaxial compression and in-plane shear, the modes of failure involved include: overstressing of the face and core elements in compression and shear, overall panel buckling in compression and shear, and the buckling of each face element and core element in compression and shear.

The results provide means to select the optimum face thickness, core depth, truss core element thickness, and its angle with respect to the faces for any material system; the means to select the best material system, and the best stacking sequence for that system.

INTRODUCTION

In order to obtain minimum weight panels composed of composite materials, optimization studies have been made of honeycomb sandwich panels subjected to in-plane compressive loads [1-3] and in-plane shear loads [4]; truss or corrugated core sandwich panels subjected to in-plane compressive loads [5] and in-plane shear loads [6]; web core sandwich panels subjected to in-plane compressive loads [7,8], and in-plane shear loads [9]; and solid or foam core sandwich panels subjected to in-plane compressive loads [10].

It was found from several numerical examples that under uniaxial compressive loads the minimum weight truss core construction is only a few percent heavier in weight than the minimum weight honeycomb core sandwich panel construction for a given applied load index where either could be employed. Incidentally, the truss core sandwich panel can withstand much higher compressive loads than can the honeycomb core construction without becoming overstressed.

However, numerical examples also indicate that under in-plane shear loads that the optimized truss core construction is significantly heavier than the minimum weight honeycomb core construction.

It is therefore surmised that if truss core sandwich panels are to be used for combined in-plane compressive and in-plane shear loads, it will be for combinations of load wherein the major loading will be the compressive loading. Otherwise the truss core construction may be inefficient compared to other alternative constructions.

It can be seen [5,6] that the optimized truss core construction for in-plane compressive loads differs from that for the in-plane shear loads. Thus, in a truss core sandwich panel optimized for in-plane compression wherein all buckling modes occur simultaneously, if that panel were subjected to in-plane shear loads only, it would not be optimum--and the various buckling modes would not occur simultaneously.

But since the truss core sandwich panel is competitive only when in-plane compressive loads dominate, it is logical to start with the optimum construction for in-plane compressive loads only, and modify the construction to account for the smaller in-plane shear loads.

OPTIMIZED COMPOSITE TRUSS CORE SANDWICH PANEL SUBJECTED TO IN-PLANE COMPRESSIVE LOADS ONLY

Consider the panel, shown in Figure 1, of length a and width b subjected to an in-plane constant compressive load N_x in lbs per unit edge distance as shown. Figure 2 indicates the face thickness t_f , core depth h_c , truss core element thickness t_c , and the angle θ . Vinson and Shore [5] have shown that for minimum weight these quantities must be determined by (1) through (4) below to attain minimum weight for a given material system.

$$\frac{t_F}{b} = \frac{6(1 - \nu_{xy}\nu_{yx})^{1/2} \sigma_0}{\pi^2 K^{1/2} E_0^{1/2} (E_x E_y)^{1/4}} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{h_C}{b} = \frac{1}{(E_x E_y)^{1/4}} \left[\frac{15}{2} \frac{\sigma_0}{\pi^2 K} \right]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{t_C}{b} = \left[\frac{7}{8} \right]^{1/2} \frac{t_F}{b} \quad (3)$$

$$\theta = 32.4^\circ \text{ (ie. } \sin^2 \theta = 2/7) \quad (4)$$

In the above, the applied load N_x is related to the optimum face stress, σ_0 , by the "universal relationship"

$$\frac{N_x}{b} = \frac{45}{2} \frac{(1 - \nu_{xy}\nu_{yx})^{1/2} \sigma_0^2}{\pi^2 K^{1/2} E_0^{1/2} (E_x E_y)^{1/4}} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{where } E_0 = \frac{1}{2} \left[(E_x E_y)^{1/2} + \nu_{yx} E_x + 2G_{xy} (1 - \nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}) \right] \quad (6)$$

In the foregoing, the values are dependent upon K , which is obtained from Figures 3 or 5 of NACA TN2679 [11] where for the optimum construction $E_c \bar{I}_c / E_f \bar{I}_f = 7/24$, and

$$V = \frac{21(1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx})\sigma_0}{(E_x E_y)^{1/2} K} \quad (7)$$

Hence, a trivial iteration may be necessary to obtain K .

From the optimum construction the weight per unit planform area W can be found most easily by

$$\frac{W - W_{ad}}{b} = \frac{N_x}{b} \frac{\rho}{\sigma_0} \quad (8)$$

where ρ is the weight density of the material, and W_{ad} is included to be a non-analytic weight per unit planform area due to an adhesive used for bonding or other assembling means.

σ_0 is the optimum face stress for this construction, and is limited by an allowable strength for the material which in turn restricts the maximum applied load N_x . If a panel is designed so that the face stress is either greater than or less than σ_0 , the panel will weigh more than the optimized construction of (1) through (5) above.

This optimized construction presented above is for the same anisotropic material used for both faces and core. To reduce it to an isotropic material is straightforward. If the face and core material differ, see [12].

COMBINED LOADS

Under combined loads of in-plane compression and in-plane shear, Gerard and Becker [13] provide an interaction relationship for the stability of a flat panel.

$$\frac{\sigma_f}{\sigma_{f_{cr}}} + \left(\frac{\tau_f}{\tau_{f_{cr}}} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (9)$$

where σ_f and $\sigma_{f_{cr}}$ are the applied and critical buckling face compressive stress, and τ_f and $\tau_{f_{cr}}$ are the applied and critical face shear stress in the panel.

From [5], the compressive face stress σ_f is related to the applied load by

$$\sigma_f = \frac{N_x}{\left[\frac{t_c}{\sin\theta} + 2t_f \right]} \quad (10)$$

which accounts for the core elements carrying a portion of the applied load.

From [6], it is seen that

$$\tau_f = N_{xy}/2t_f \quad (11)$$

For the optimum construction subscripts cr can be applied to σ_f , N_x , τ_f and N_{xy} to denote the values causing buckling.

$$\frac{N_x/b}{N_{xcr}/b} + \frac{(N_{xy}/b)^2}{(N_{xycr}/b)^2} = 1 \quad (12)$$

OPTIMIZATION UNDER COMBINED LOADS

Using the truss core sandwich proportioned optimally designed for in-plane compressive load acting only, when N_{xcr}/b is achieved, there will be simultaneous buckling of that panel in overall buckling, face plate buckling and web plate buckling. However, for that panel optimized for compressive loads only, when shear loads N_{xy} are applied, the three buckling modes in shear will not occur simultaneously, because that panel is not optimum for the shear loads. It is therefore necessary to determine which shear buckling mode will occur first.

Substituting the expressions (1) through (4) into the three expressions for stability for that panel subjected to in-plane shear loads [6], it is found that the truss core sandwich panel proportioned optimally for compressive loads will undergo face plate buckling first as shear loads N_{xy} (only) are applied.

If (1) through (4) are substituted into the face panel buckling equation due to shear loads given in [6], then (12) above can be written as:

$$\frac{N_{xy_{cr}}}{b} = \frac{8}{15} \frac{k_F}{\pi^2} \frac{(E_x E_y)^{1/4}}{E_0} \frac{N_{x_{cr}}}{b} \quad (13)$$

Here, k_F is a constant, easily determined from Figure 9-42 from Timoshenko and Gere [14].

Defining the following quantities,

$$\phi = \frac{8}{15} \frac{k_F}{\pi^2} \frac{(E_x E_y^3)^{1/4}}{E_0} \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha = N_{xy}/N_x \quad (14)$$

substituting (13) and (14) into (12) gives

$$(N_{x_{cr}}/b)^2 - (N_x/b)(N_{x_{cr}}/b) - \frac{\alpha^2}{\phi^2} (N_x/b)^2 = 0 \quad (15)$$

The solution of (15) is

$$\frac{N_{x_{cr}}}{b} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{N_x}{b} \right) \left[1 + \left(1 + \frac{4\alpha^2}{\phi^2} \right)^{1/2} \right] \quad (16)$$

Note that if no shear loads are applied, $\alpha = 0$ and $N_x = N_{x_{cr}}$, i.e. the panel is optimum for in-plane axial loads wherein simultaneous buckling of all three modes will occur. When $\alpha > 0$ the panel must be designed for a critical value of $N_{x_{cr}}$ greater than that when no shear loads are present.

Looking at the functional relationships for the panel in terms of the applied load N_x , i.e. solving for σ_0 in (5) and substituting that value into (1) through (4) and (8), it is seen that (t_F/b) , (t_C/b) and $(w-w_{ad})/b$ are proportional to $(N_{x_{cr}}/b)^{1/2}$ while (h_C/b) is proportional to $(N_{x_{cr}}/b)^{1/4}$.

Therefore to optimize the truss core sandwich panel for simultaneously applied in-plane compressive loads and in-plane shear loads, where the former are the major load, one modifies the optimum construction of (1) through (8) to be:

$$\begin{bmatrix} t_f/b \\ t_c/b \\ \frac{W-W_{ad}}{b} \end{bmatrix}_{\substack{N_x \text{ given} \\ N_{xy} \text{ given}}} = \begin{bmatrix} t_f/b \\ t_c/b \\ \frac{W-W_{ad}}{b} \end{bmatrix}_{\substack{N_x \text{ given} \\ N_{xy} = 0}} \left(\frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \left(1 + \frac{4\alpha^2}{\phi^2} \right)^{1/2} \right] \right)^{1/2} \quad (17)$$

$$(h_c/b)_{\substack{N_x \text{ given} \\ N_{xy} \text{ given}}} = (h_c/b)_{\substack{N_x \text{ given} \\ N_{xy} = 0}} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \left(1 + \frac{4\alpha^2}{\phi^2} \right)^{1/2} \right] \right\}^{1/4} \quad (18)$$

EXAMPLE OF PENALTIES INVOLVED

From (17) & (18) the modifications to the various parameters can be shown lucidly as follows:

α	$\left\{ \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \left(1 + 4 \frac{\alpha^2}{\phi^2} \right)^{1/2} \right] \right\}^{1/2}$	$\left\{ \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \left(1 + 4 \frac{\alpha^2}{\phi^2} \right)^{1/2} \right] \right\}^{1/4}$
0	1.000	1.00
0.2	1.036	1.02
0.4	1.12	1.06
0.6	1.218	1.10
0.8	1.315	1.15
1.0	1.413	1.19

It must be remembered that when the combined loads are applied to the optimized construction, the combined stress in the face and web elements must be calculated, and a suitable failure theory utilized to prevent

overstressing. Overstressing will determine the maximum loads that can be applied to the optimized construction to avoid both buckling and overstressing.

OPTIMUM DESIGN PROCEDURES

1. Given N_x , N_{xy} , a and b
2. Select material system and obtain all material properties needed.
3. Letting N_x above be the critical load when no shear loading is acting, use (5) to determine the optimum face stress σ_o .
4. If it is below the allowable compressive strength of the material then use (1) through (8) to obtain the optimum values for t_f/b , t_c/b , h_c/b , and $(W-W_{ad})/b$.
5. Determine ϕ from (14).
6. Calculate α from (14).
7. Determine the minimum weight truss core panel component dimensions and weight from (17) and (18).

CONCLUSIONS

Methods have been developed herein to design the minimum weight truss core sandwich panel of composite materials for given planform dimensions and any given materials system, for applied combined in-plane compressive loads and shear loads. The methods vary the panel component dimensions from the minimum weight configuration for in-plane compressive loads alone to account for those loads combined with in-plane shear loads. Such a procedure is possible where the compressive loads are dominant, which is the condition where truss core sandwich is competitive with alternative constructions.

These optimization procedures are useful to:

1. select the best composite or other material system to obtain minimum weight for a given load combination and set of panel boundary conditions.
2. select the best stacking sequence for a given materials system.
3. compare the relative weights associated with various boundary conditions.
4. compare truss core sandwich design with other panel architectures to obtain minimum weight panels subjected to these simultaneous loads.

5. compare the relative weights of continuous fiber composites with other systems such as chopped fibers, textile composites, 3D composites, etc.
6. rationally assess the weight penalties associated with non-optimum construction due to constraints of manufacturing, environment, minimum gage, cost, etc.

REFERENCES

1. Vinson, J. R., "Optimum Design of Composite Hex-Cell and Square Cell Honeycomb Sandwich Panels Subjected to Uniaxial Compression," AIAA Journal, August, 1986.
2. Vinson, J. R., "Minimum Weight Composite Material Honeycomb Sandwich Panels Under Uniaxial Compression," Transactions of the First European Conference on Composite Materials, Bordeaux, September, 1985.
3. Vinson, J. R. and R. L. Sierakowski, The Behavior of Structures of Composite Materials, Martinus-Nijhoff, Dordrecht, 1986.
4. Vinson, J. R., "Minimum Weight Composite Honeycomb Core Sandwich Panels Subjected to In-Plane Shear Loads," accepted for publication.
5. Vinson, J. R. and S. Shore, "Minimum Weight Corrugated Core Sandwich Panels Subjected to Uniaxial Compression," International Journal of Fibre Science and Technology, 1968.
6. Vinson, J. R., "Minimum Weight Triangulated (Truss) Core Sandwich Panels Subjected to In-Plane Shear Loads," Transactions of the Third Japan-U.S. Conference on Composite Materials, Tokyo, June 1986.
7. Vinson, J. R. and S. Shore, "Minimum Weight Web Core Sandwich Panels Subjected to Uniaxial Compression," AIAA Journal of Aircraft, 8, 11, pp. 843-847, November, 1971.
8. Vinson, J. R., "Minimum Weight Web-Core Composite Sandwich Panels Subjected to In-Plane Compressive Loads," Transactions of the International Symposium on Composite Materials and Structures, Beijing, June 1986.
9. Vinson, J. R., "Minimum Weight Web-Core Composite Sandwich Panels Subjected to In-Plane Shear Loads," submitted for publication.
10. Vinson, J. R., "Minimum Weight Solid Core Composite Sandwich Panels Subjected to In-Plane Compressive Loads," submitted for publication.
11. Seide, Paul, "The Stability Under Longitudinal Compression of Flat Symmetric Corrugated-Core Sandwich Plates with Simply Supported Loaded Edges and Simply Supported or Clamped Unloaded Edges," NACA TN 2679, April 1952.

12. Vinson, J. R. and Shore, S., "Structural Optimization of Corrugated Core and Web Core Sandwich Panels Subjected to Uniaxial Compression," US NAEC-ASL 1109, May 1967.
13. Gerard, G. and Becker, H., "Handbook of Structural Stability, Part III, Buckling of Curved Plates and Shells," NACA TN 3783, August, 1957.
14. Timoshenko, S. and Gere, J. M., "Theory of Elastic Stability," 2nd Edition, McGraw-Hill Book Co., Inc., New York, 1961.

Fig. 1 - Planform View of Panel

Fig. 2 - Triangulated Core Sandwich